

Assessing the Extent of Digitalization in the Management of Education in Private and Public Secondary Schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State

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Abstract

The study assessed the extent of digitalization in the management of education in private and public secondary schools in Port Harcourt metropolis of Rivers State. Descriptive survey design was adopted with two research questions and two hypotheses as research guides. The population of the study consisted of 4,500 teachers in government approved leading private secondary schools and public secondary schools in Port Harcourt metropolis. A sample of 280 private school teachers and 170 public school teachers constituting 10% of the population was drawn through proportionate stratified random sampling technique. A questionnaire instrument titled: “Assessment of Extent of Digitalization in Management of Education in Private and Public Secondary Schools in Port Harcourt metropolis (AEDMEPPS” developed by the researcher was used for data collection. The instrument which contained 20 items was well validated and tested for reliability using Cronbach Alfa method with a reliability index of 0.81. Mean standard deviation were used to analyze the research questions while z-test at 0.05 level of significance was used in testing the hypotheses. The results of the study showed that, the extent of digitalization in the management of education in the leading private secondary schools in Port Harcourt metropolis is high, while that of public secondary schools is low. The challenges of digitalization in the management of secondary education in Port Harcourt metropolis among others include: inadequate provision of ICT/digital facilities and high cost of maintenance of ICT/digital facilities. Based on the findings conclusion was drawn and the following recommendations among others were made: secondary education regulatory bodies, stakeholders and owners of private secondary schools in Port Harcourt metropolis should ensure adequate provision of ICT/digital facilities and the maintenance of minimum standards in the use of these facilities for quality education delivery.

Keywords: *Digitalization, secondary education, public schools, private schools, and Port Harcourt Metropolis.*

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Introduction

The introduction of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) into education management and practices is increasing consistently and is enhancing quality service delivery. ICT incorporation in the educational system accompanied by other modern technologies has given rise to digitalization of educational management system. The digitalization of the management of education has the potential of transforming the way we administer schools, teach and learn. Digitalization of the management of educational institutions such as secondary schools is necessary because a strong information system support is quite essential for meaningful progress, efficiency and effectiveness in the management of secondary schools. It has been argued by Yusuf (2005) that the ability of modern organisations to attain their set goals and the decision-making efficacy of contemporary managers is no longer dependent on

just the qualities of the managers but more importantly it is a function of the quality of information channels feeding and transmitting their actions.

Digitalizing the management of secondary education requires the full entrenchment and adoption of emerging components of information and communication technologies (ICT) in the planning, execution, and evaluation of the goals and objectives of secondary education. ICT is the convergence of computer system with telecommunication networks to acquire, process, store, retrieve and transmit data and information. Digitalization involves information storage facilities such as computer disc read only memory (CD-ROM), magnetic tapes, computer files, databases, networks, internet-based tools and technologies, hosting of websites etc., which have emerged to meet the students and societal needs. The impact and growth of digital technologies which has turned the world into a global village has equally impacted positively in the education sector. It has simplified the teaching and learning process and has enhanced efficient and effective transmission of information, knowledge and skills.

Secondary education is a very important level of education all over the world. It is the education children receive after primary education and before the tertiary or higher education (FRN, 2014). The broad goals of secondary education is to prepare its recipients for useful living within the society; and for higher education. It is difficult to talk about impacting knowledge, vocational and technical skills that will promote useful living among contemporary secondary school graduates without equipping the students with digital skills which will help them take advantage of digital technology and digital tools around them. Digital tools and technologies have been found useful in the administration and management of schools in terms of students and staff personnel management, financial management, teaching and learning, administration of examinations, dissemination of information etc.

Secondary schools in Nigeria are classified into public and private schools. Public secondary school are those secondary schools that are built and funded by either the state or federal government. They are funded with public funds. While private secondary schools are those secondary schools that are built, funded and managed by the individuals, churches or organisations that built them. Government through the ministry of education regulates the operations of secondary schools and ensures that they adhere to minimum standards for the operation of secondary schools and the implementation of secondary school curriculum.

The incorporation of digital technology in the management of today's secondary schools is very necessary for qualitative, efficient and effective service delivery. It is equally necessary to enable secondary schools meet the needs of the students and that of the society. Port Harcourt metropolis comprises of Port Harcourt City Local Government Area (LGA), Obio/Akpor Local Government Area and some parts of Ikwerre and Eleme Local Government Areas. The researcher is not too sure of the extent to which public and private secondary schools in these LGA's have adopted digital technology in the management of educational practices, hence the motivation to carry out this study.

Statement of the Problems

The world today is conceptualized as a global village due to innovations brought about by modern technology. Global standards in education demands that students and teachers need to acquire functional skills and a growing ambition not only to succeed in life but to contribute and benefit from the global economy. This cannot be achieved through the use of traditional and antiquated methods of educational management. Our educational system must endeavor to follow the digital trend of the 21st century. If secondary schools in Rivers State will produce global digital citizens, the management process of our secondary education also needs to be digitalized. The researcher is not sure of the extent of digitalization of the management of secondary education in Port Harcourt Metropolis in this era of globalization.

The researcher sees this as a problem. Hence, the problem of this study is to assess the extent of digitalization of the management of education in public and private secondary schools in Port Harcourt metropolis of Rivers state.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of this study was to assess the extent of digitalization in the management of education in public and private secondary schools in Port Harcourt metropolis of Rivers State. In specific terms, the objectives of the study were to:

1. Assess the extent of utilization of information communication and technology (ICT) and other digital tools in the management of education in public and private secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State.
2. Identify the challenges of utilizing ICT and other digital tools in the management of education in public and private secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State.

Research Questions

1. To what extent are ICT and other digital tools utilized in the management of education in public and private secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State?
2. What are the challenges of utilizing ICT and other digital tools in the management of education in public and private secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State?

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference between the mean scores of private and public secondary school teachers in Port Harcourt Metropolis on the extent of utilization of ICT and other digital tools in the management of education in their schools.
2. There is no significant difference between the mean scores of private and public secondary school teachers in Port Harcourt Metropolis on the challenges of utilizing ICT and other digital tools in the management of education in their schools.

Literature Review

Digitalization of the management of secondary education is a major improvement made in the educational industry to improve the provision and management of secondary education. Digitalization of education has evolved for numerous reasons. According to Oguiche (2013) one of the major reasons is that education can no longer be confined in the four walls of the classroom knowledge is vast, and students need to put their curiosity, exploration, creative skills and innovative ideas into practice. Our traditional methods of education cannot adequately cater for the students' needs in this information and technology age. Digital facilities must be provided and made available for students' use in the secondary schools to expose them to modern technology, information and communication system.

Digitalization as defined by Oiga (2017), and Daniel (2020) as the transformation of all types of information texts, sounds, visual, video and other data from various sources into digital language. According to Oiga (2017), it involves the use of advance technique to introduce online courses, online examinations, digital textbooks, animation, accumulation of students on the same platform and connecting students with their educators.

To digitalize secondary education, we need essential digital tools and equipment such as learning management systems (LMS) like canvas, interactive whiteboards, students devices like laptops and tablets, document cameras, video conferencing platforms, digital textbooks, educational apps, online collaboration tools and robust internet connectivity, which allow teachers to deliver engaging content, facilitate remote learning and personalize student experiences (<https://www.researchgate.net>), and (Ray, 2020)..

Education in the 21st century according to Danca, Stempel Ova, Takac and Annus (2023) aims at creating an educational paradigm that prepares tomorrow's workforce for the challenges of tomorrow. This

include technical, methodological, social and personal competences. To ensure that future employees emerging from the education process are able to use new digital tools and constantly update their knowledge as technology evolves rapidly.

Integrating technology in the classrooms not only cultivates digital literacy skills but also fosters collaborative and personalized learning environments. Digitalization of education helps students to explore the multifaceted nature of technology tools, highlighting their transformative impact on the teaching and learning process. Olachukwu (2022) investigated public and private secondary schools administrators' efficiency.

Olachukwu (2022) investigated public and private secondary schools administrators' efficiency towards utilization of emerging technologies for managing educational processes in Anambra State. The findings of the study revealed among others that although many of the administrators in both public and private schools were inefficient in utilizing emerging technologies, the private secondary school administrators were efficient towards the utilization of most of the emerging hardware technologies for managing educational processes in Anambra state more than the public secondary school administrators. In another related study by Ali, Ashraf and Yasmin (2020) on inequalities of digital skills and innovation: an analysis of public and private schools, vary a lot in the use of digital skills. The study noted that private schools were more innovative in accessing digital skills.

Ikedingwu and Anyanwu (2019) carried out a study on comparative analysis of principals' ICT competencies for management of information system in public and private secondary schools in Anambra State. The findings of the study were that: in web based/networking, private school principals were very competent while principals of public schools were not, in data base management, public secondary school principals were not competent while private school principals were moderately competent,. It was also found that there was significant difference in the mean competency scores of public and private secondary school principals in web base/networking competency.

Digitalization of education in Nigeria is challenged by so many factors which include: poor funding of education, shortage of digital facilities, power problem, poor internet connectivity, high cost of digital facilities, poor digital skills and knowledge, and shortage of digital experts, poor implementation problems, corruption and resistance to change (Ukozor & Muhammad, 2024).

Oguche, Adejoh and Akoji (2023) submitted that every area of secondary school can be digitalized and that digitalization of education in public secondary schools in Kogi East is at a very low extent. Corroborating this view Bello (2013) asserted that primary and secondary schools in Nigeria are yet to fully adopt digitalization and that, this situation has negative effects on their operations and quality education delivery. Many schools in Port Harcourt metropolis do not have adequate information and communication technology (ICT) facilities and this indicates that they are not fully digitalized.

Digitalization of secondary education has enormous benefits. According to Akinyemi, Amaechi and Etoh (2022) the benefits of digitalization of secondary education include the following: improved access to educational resources and programs, personalized learning approaches, virtual reality, cloud-based learning opportunities and teaching digital citizens. It equally improves learning efficiency, reduces the burden on teachers, simplifies information sharing, increases student motivation and it improves IT literacy of students.

Despite the lofty benefits of digitalization of secondary education, there are numerous factors hindering digitalization of secondary education in Nigeria. Aganyi, Jacob and Ayoko (2023) identified inadequate funding, shortage of technological facilities, unstable power supply, poor internet services, shortage of computer teachers, poor implementation of ICT policies, poor ICT literacy of students, high cost of ICT facilities, lack of technical support for repair and maintenance of ICT facilities, corruption and insecurity as factors challenging digitalization of education as in Nigeria.

Methodology

The researcher adopted descriptive survey design. The design is considered adequate for the study because it allowed the researcher to collect data from the teachers at their convenience and according to what is obtainable in their schools without any manipulation. The study was carried out in the Port Harcourt metropolis of Rivers State. The population of the study comprised of 4,500 teachers in government approved leading private secondary schools and public secondary schools in Port Harcourt metropolis of Rivers State (2,800 private school teachers and 1,700 public secondary school teachers). A sample of 450 teachers (280 private school teachers and 170 public school teachers) which is 10% of the total population was used. Proportionate stratified random sampling technique was used and each secondary school in the area was classified into strata.

The instrument for data collection was a questionnaire entitled: “Assessment of Extent of Digitalization of Management of Education in private and public secondary schools in Port Harcourt metropolis of Rivers State (AEDMEPPSS)” which was developed by the researcher. The instrument was tested for reliability using Cronbach Alpha method. This yielded a reliability index of 0.81 indicating that the instrument was reliable. Three experts validated the instrument for face and content validity, one from Educational Management, one from ICT education and the third person was from Education Measurement and Evaluation, Rivers State University, Nkpolu Oruworukwo. four hundred and fifty (450) copies of the questionnaire were administered to the respondents and retrieved from them. The research questions were analyzed using weighted mean and standard deviation. While z-test at 0.05 level of significance was used to test the hypotheses. To answer the research questions, real limit mean values of 0.5-1.49, 1.50-2.49, 2.50 – 3.49, and 3.50-4.00 were used to interpret the results as very low extent (VLE), low extent (LE), High Extent (HE) and Very High Extent (VHE), and strongly Disagree (SD), Disagree (D), Agree (A) and Strongly Agree (SA) respectively.

Results

Researcher Question 1: To what extent are ICT and other digital tools utilized in the management of education in public and private secondary schools in Port Harcourt metropolis of Rivers State?

Table 1. Mean Scores and Standard Deviation Analysis of the Opinion of Leading Private Secondary School Teachers and Public Secondary School Teachers on the Extent ICT and Other Digital Tools are Utilized in the Management of Education in Public and Private Secondary Schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State

S/N	Extent of digitalization the management of education in Port Harcourt Metropolis	Leading private secondary school teachers N = 280		Decision	Public secondary school teachers N = 170		Decision
		\bar{x}_1	SD ₁		\bar{x}_2	SD ₂	
1	To what extent are test and examinations computer based in your schools?	3.05	0.72	HE	2.40	0.87	LE
2	To what extent do students assess their assignments and submit them online?	3.00	0.74	HE	1.44	1.02	VLE
3	To what extent is every student in your school expected to have a laptop or a tablet?	3.06	0.70	HE	2.08	0.94	LE
4	To what extent are students results continues assessments and other records accessed online in your school?	3.24	0.68	HE	2.30	0.98	LE
5.	To what extent are lesson plans prepared and submitted online by teachers for	3.20	0.69	HE	1.42	1.06	VLE

	school authorities to go through and approved?						
6.	To what extent are lesson notes prepared and submitted online by teachers for school authorities and students to access?	3.20	0.69	HE	1.42	1.06	VLE
7	To what extent does your school communicate with parents and other people through emails and school websites?	3.30	0.67	HE	2.34	0.91	LE
8	To what extent does your school have a functional website and a digital learning management system?	2.80	0.81	HE	2.10	0.97	LE
9	To what extents does your school have interactive white boards, document cameras, digital/e-learning, textbooks, online collaborative tools and adequate internet connectivity?	2.70	0.86	HE	1.80	1.03	LE
10	To what extent does every class in your school have a video conferencing and whatsapp platforms?	2.84	0.80	HE	1.88	1.00	LE
	Aggregate mean and standard deviation	3.04	0.74		1.92	0.98	

Table 1 shows that the mean scores of leading private secondary school teachers in Port Harcourt metropolis ranged from 2.70 to 3.30, which indicates a high extent (HE) in all the ten items on the table while, the mean scores of public secondary school teachers ranged from 1.42 to 2.40, which indicates very low extent (VLE) to low extent (LE) with items 5 and 6 recording VLE and the rest LE. Therefore, the extent of digitalization in the management of education in the private secondary schools in Port Harcourt metropolis is high, while that of public secondary schools is low.

Research Question 2: What are the challenges of utilizing ICT and other digital tools in the management of education in public and private secondary schools in Port Harcourt metropolis?

Table 2. Mean Scores and Standard Deviation Analysis of the Opinion of Leading Private Secondary School Teachers and Public Secondary School Teachers on the Challenges of Utilizing ICT and Other Digital Tools in the Management of Education in Public and Private Secondary Schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis

S/N	Challenges	Leading private secondary school teachers N = 280		Decision	Public secondary school teachers N = 170		Decision
		\bar{x}_1	SD ₁		\bar{x}_2	SD ₂	
1	Inadequate provision of ICT/Digital facilities in secondary schools	2.80	0.69	Agree	3.60	0.63	Agree
2	Inadequate power supply	3.45	0.60	Agree	3.54	0.66	Agree
3	High cost of alternative power supply	3.50	0.59	Agree	3.56	0.65	Agree
4	Inadequate funding of education	2.36	0.74	Disagree	3.62	0.62	Agree
5.	Inadequate internet services	3.08	0.65	Agree	3.48	0.70	Agree
6.	Inadequate ICT skills of teachers	3.16	0.64	Agree	3.50	0.68	Agree
7	High cost of ICT/digital facilities	3.20	0.62	Agree	3.38	0.72	Agree
8	High cost of maintenance of ICT/Digital facilities	3.20	0.62	Agree	3.30	0.74	Agree
9	Corruption	2.40	0.72	Disagree	3.64	0.61	Agree
10	Poor ICT literacy of students teaching and non teaching staff	2.88	0.67	Agree	3.44	0.71	Agree
	Aggregate mean and standard deviation	3.00	0.65		3.51	0.67	

Table 2 shows that leading private school teachers agreed on all the items as the challenges facing digitalization of the management of education in their schools except items 4 and 9. While public secondary school teachers agreed on all the items (1-10) as the challenges of digitalization of the management of education in public secondary schools in Port Harcourt metropolis. The aggregate mean score of 3.00 for private secondary school teachers and 3.57 for public secondary school teachers which are above the criterion mean indicate that the respondents shared a common opinions on the challenges of digitalization of the management of secondary education in Port Harcourt metropolis of Rivers State.

Therefore, the challenges of digitalization in the management of secondary education in Port Harcourt metropolis of Rivers State include: inadequate provision of ICT/Digital facilities, inadequate power supply, high cost of alternative power supply, inadequate internet services, inadequate ICT skills of teachers, high cost of ICT/Digital facilities, high cost of maintenance of ICT/Digital facilities, and poor ICT literacy of staff and student personnel. In addition to these factors, public secondary schools are equally faced with the challenges of poor funding and corruption.

Test of Hypotheses

H0₁: There is no significant difference between the mean scores of private secondary school and public secondary school teachers in Port Harcourt metropolis on the extent of utilization of ICT and other digital tools in the management of education in their schools.

Table 3. z-Test of Difference between the Mean Scores of Private and Public Secondary School Teachers in Port Harcourt Metropolis on the Extent of Utilization of ICT and Other Digital Tools in the Management of Education in Their Schools

Status	N	Mean	SD	Df	Z-cal	Critical z-value	Level of Sign.	Decision
Private secondary school teachers	280	3.04	0.74		12.844	±1.960	0.05	H0 ₁ is significant
				448				Null hypothesis rejected
Public secondary school teachers	170	1.92	0.98					

Table 3 shows the summary of mean, standard deviation and z-test of difference between the private and public secondary school teachers in Port Harcourt metropolis on the extent of utilization of ICT and other digital tools in the management of education in their schools. The z-test calculated which was used in testing the hypothesis stood at 12.844 while the critical z-value was 1.960 at 448 degree of freedom, using 0.05 level of significance. The z-calculated was by far greater than the z-critical value. Therefore the null hypothesis of no significant difference between the means scores of private and public secondary school teachers in Port Harcourt metropolis on the extent of utilization of ICT and other digital tools in the management of education in their schools was rejected. This implies that, there is significant difference on the extent of utilization of ICT and other digital tools in the management of education in private and public secondary schools in Port Harcourt metropolis of Rivers State.

H0₂: There is no significant difference between the means scores of private and public secondary school teachers in Port Harcourt metropolis on the challenges of utilizing ICT and other digital tools in the management of education in their schools.

Table 4: z-Test of Difference between the Mean Scores of Private and Public Secondary School Teachers in Port Harcourt Metropolis on the Challenges of Utilizing ICT and Other Digital Tools in the Management of Education in Their Schools

Status	N	Mean	SD	Df	Z-cal	Critical z-value	Level of Sign.	Decision
Private secondary school teachers	280	3.00	0.65		7.917	± 1.960	0.05	H02 is significant.
				448				Null hypothesis rejected
Public secondary school teachers	170	3.51	0.67					

Table 4 shows the summary of mean, standard deviation and z-test of difference between the private and public secondary school teachers in Port Harcourt metropolis on the challenges of utilizing ICT and other digital tools in the management of education in their schools. The z-test calculated which was used in testing the hypothesis stood at 7.917, while the critical z-value was 1.960 at 448 degree of freedom using 0.05 level of significance. The z-calculated was by far greater than the z-critical value. Therefore, the null hypothesis of no significant difference between the mean scores of private and public secondary school teachers in Port Harcourt metropolis on the challenges of utilizing ICT and other digital tools in the management of education in their schools was rejected. This implies that, there is a significant difference in the challenges of utilizing ICT and other digital tools in the management of education in private and public secondary schools in Port Harcourt metropolis of Rivers State.

Discussion of Findings

The study assessed the extent of digitalization in the management of education in private and public secondary schools in Port Harcourt metropolis of Rivers State. The results revealed that, the extent of digitalization in the management of education in the leading private secondary schools in the study area is high while that of public secondary schools is low. These findings are in agreement with Olachukwu (2022), Ali, Asharf and Yasmen (2020), and Ikediugwu and Anyanwu (2019) who in their respective studies observed that private secondary schools were more efficient in the utilization of emerging technologies in the management of educational processes than public schools; private secondary schools are more innovative in accessing digital skills than public secondary schools; and that private secondary school administrators were more competent in web base/networking and database management more than public secondary school administrators.

Leading private secondary schools in Port Harcourt metropolis have equipped ICT/computer laboratories, where students learn. They have their websites through which members of the public can access information about their school. In some of these schools teachers write and submit their lesson plan/lesson notes online, student assignments are given and submitted online, and students' results, personal information, and continuous assessment records are accessed online. Students are encouraged to interact with their school authorities, teachers and fellow students through digital tools such as emails, whatsapp, video conference /zoom meeting etc. On the contrary, most of these services are not available in public secondary schools.

There is high level of competition among private secondary schools in Port Harcourt metropolis unlike public secondary schools. This competition creates room for constant innovations, training of staff, creativity and adoption of modern technologies. They look at ways of meeting global standards in the provision of secondary education. Some of these schools operate blended school curriculum and they recognize the fact that technology is changing the world around us and the methods of educational service

delivery. Hence, the reason for a paradigm shift to the use of technology in education. Digitalization of educational processes makes teaching and learning more creative, more engaging, more innovative and even more enjoyable.

These findings are equally in agreement with Oguche, Adejoh and Akoji (2023) as well as Bello (2013). These researchers submitted that every aspect of secondary education can be digitalized and that digitalization of education in public primary and secondary schools in Nigeria is at a very low extent. This situation does not support adequate school operations and quality education delivery. Recognizing the need for digitalization and the benefits accruing from it, the Hon. Minister for Education Dr. Olatunju Alausa inaugurated a committee to work on migration of examinations conducted by West African Examination Council (WAEC), National Examination Council (NECO) and National Business and Technical Examination Board (NABTEB) among others, from current paper based examination to Computer Based Test (CBT) in the next three years. According to the Minister, we have to leverage on technology to enhance the quality of education and examinations in the country.

The study revealed that the challenges of digitalization in the management of secondary education in Port Harcourt metropolis include: lack of adequate provision of ICT/digital facilities, poor power supply; escalating cost of alternative power supply, poor internet facilities, lack of required ICT skills among teachers, high cost of ICT/digital facilities, high cost of maintenance, poor funding of secondary education, corruption, and inadequate ICT literacy of staff and student personnel. These findings align with Ukozor and Muhammad (2024), as well as Ajayi, Jacob and Ayoko (2023). ICT/digital facilities are costly and their provision is cost intensive. Most of the digital facilities if not all are imported and their value relies so much on the exchange rate. The current high exchange rate and import duty affects adequate provision of these facilities.

The inadequate provision of these facilities is worst in public secondary schools because of poor funding of secondary education, corruption and inadequate care and maintenance of public facilities. Unlike private secondary schools where school fees collected are used in funding the school and maintenance of school facilities. Public schools are funded by government and secondary education is highly subsidized. School administrators do not have direct access to school funds. They apply for funds to schools' Board and Ministry of Education who respond at their own time and may not provide enough money for the schools, to meet their needs. Sometimes, the money released to the schools may be diverted by the school administrators. They may cut corners and inflate the costs. Corruption in the administration of secondary education in Nigeria has grossly affected the installation of digital facilities and other developments in public secondary schools in Nigeria.

The issue of maintenance and supervision of the utilization of digital facilities is another factor. While private school administrators pay adequate attention on the issue of maintenance, replacement of damaged parts and supervision of the utilization of school facilities, public school administrators do not. The care free attitude on public facilities in public secondary schools results to frequent breakdown of school facilities and short life span of these facilities. Power supply is a serious challenge in Nigeria. It has affected digitalization of education in Nigeria, especially in public schools. All digital facilities require adequate power supply to function effectively. Digitalization of education cannot be possible without electricity, and the supply of this is not adequately guaranteed in Nigeria. The high cost of alternative power supply is another issue. Many schools (private and public) cannot afford power generating sets and those that have cannot adequately utilize them because of high cost of petrol, diesel and spare parts.

Internet connection is another major problem. Poor internet connection across Nigeria has affected digitalization of secondary education. It serves as a major barrier in the integration of educational institutions into e-learning programmes. Also, the level of digital literacy of staff and students in Nigeria is low. Digital literacy has become indispensable for all students and teachers to communicate, carryout academic work, write exams and carryout research. Digital literacy is compulsory for staff and students

who want to benefit from digital facilities. Most teachers and students lack required ICT knowledge and skills

Conclusion

This paper assessed the extent of digitalization in the management of education in private and public secondary schools in Port Harcourt metropolis, Rivers State. The paper concluded that, the extent of digitalization in the management of education in the leading private secondary schools in the study area is high, while that of public secondary schools in the same area is low. The challenges of digitalization in the management of secondary education in the study area are inadequate provision of ICT/digital facilities, inadequate power supply, inadequate internet network, poor funding, corruption, inadequate ICT skills, high cost of ICT/digital facilities and high cost of maintenance, and adequate attention must be paid to address these issues in order to enhance digitalization in the management of secondary education in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations were made:

1. Government should enhance the extent of digitalization in the management of secondary education in public secondary schools in Port Harcourt metropolis through adequate provision of ICT/digital facilities and in-service training to promote digital skills among secondary school teachers
2. Secondary education regulatory bodies stakeholders, and owners of private secondary schools in Port Harcourt metropolis should ensure adequate provision of ICT/digital facilities and the maintenance of minimum standards in the use of these facilities for quality education delivery.
3. Government should subsidize the cost of digital facilities for private and public secondary schools
4. Adequate improvement on power supply and provision of internet services should be achieved by government to enhance digitalization of secondary education in Port Harcourt metropolis
5. Government should make more funds available for the funding of public secondary schools and adequate measures should be made to enhance efficient and effective utilization of these funds.

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